

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>**Research Article****PREVALENCE OF DIABETES IN OUTDOOR PATIENTS**Shahid Hussain¹, Saima Naz², Raisa Maryam³¹Basic Health Unit Murghai²Fatima Jinnah Medical University³Dow Medical College Karachi**Article Received:** November 2019 **Accepted:** December 2019 **Published:** January 2020**Abstract:**

Diabetes mellitus (DM), commonly known as diabetes, is a group of metabolic disorders characterized by a high blood sugar level over a prolonged period of time. In this cross-sectional study, a total of 140 outdoor patients presenting with symptoms of frequent urination, increased thirst and increased dietary habits were included. The mean age of the patients was 33.32±3.23 years. There were 85 (60.72%) males and 55 (39.28%) females. The mean sugar level was 142.24±22.23 mg/dl. In outdoor patients presenting with symptoms of frequent urination, increased thirst and increased dietary habits, diabetes was found more often.

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Please cite this article in press Shahid Hussain et al., *Prevalence Of Diabetes In Outdoor Patients.., Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2020; 07(01).*

INTRODUCTION:

Diabetes mellitus (DM), commonly known as diabetes, is a group of metabolic disorders characterized by a high blood sugar level over a prolonged period of time. Symptoms often include frequent urination, increased thirst, and increased hunger. If left untreated, diabetes can cause many complications. Acute complications can include diabetic ketoacidosis, hyperosmolar hyperglycemic state, or death. Serious long-term complications include cardiovascular disease, stroke, chronic kidney disease, foot ulcers, damage to the nerves, and damage to the eyes (1, 2).

Type 2 diabetes mellitus (DM) is a progressive disease characterized by prolonged hyperinsulinemia, development of insulin resistance, and eventual emergence of hyperglycemia. Hyperglycemia characterizes overt DM, and disease management is focused on glycemic control through a combination of diet, exercise, and pharmacological therapy. Serum glucose concentrations in patients with DM have been linked to promotion of tumor cell proliferation and migration *in vitro*. However, recent evidence suggests that the hyperglycemia characteristic of DM may be less important in promoting cancer risk than the hyperinsulinemia characteristic of the prediabetes phase (3-5).

Prevention and treatment involve maintaining a healthy diet, regular physical exercise, a normal body weight, and avoiding use of tobacco. Control

of blood pressure, maintaining proper foot care, and eye care are important for people with the disease. Type 1 diabetes must be managed with insulin injections. Type 2 diabetes may be treated with medications with or without insulin. Insulin and some oral medications can cause low blood sugar. Weight loss surgery in those with obesity is sometimes an effective measure in those with type 2 diabetes. Gestational diabetes usually resolves after the birth of the baby (6, 7). In this study we will see the prevalence of diabetes among the outdoor patients.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

In this cross-sectional study, a total of 140 outdoor patients presenting with symptoms of frequent urination, increased thirst and increased dietary habits were included. All the data were entered and analyzed in SPSS Ver. 25.0. The qualitative variables were presented as percentages and frequencies. The quantitative variables were presented as mean and standard deviation.

RESULTS:

The mean age of the patients was 33.32 ± 3.23 years, mean age of the male patients was 34.35 ± 3.43 years and of female patients was 32.78 ± 2.32 years. There were 85 (60.72%) males and 55 (39.28%) females. The mean sugar level was 142.24 ± 22.23 mg/dl. Distribution of male and female patients according to diabetic and non-diabetic is presented in the graph:

DISCUSSION:

Type 2 diabetes—which accounts for 85–90% of all cases worldwide—can often be prevented or delayed by maintaining a normal body weight, engaging in physical activity, and eating a healthy diet. Higher levels of physical activity (more than 90 minutes per day) reduce the risk of diabetes by 28%. Glycemic control and the medications used to achieve control vary among patients with DM. Similarly, the association between glycemic control and cancer risk appears to vary by both cancer type and glucose-lowering medication(s) used (1, 5).

Previous studies suggest that, in general, tighter glycemic control does not reduce cancer risk, and that the effects of glucose-lowering medications are more likely to be the result of influence on levels of circulating insulin. Dietary changes known to be effective in helping to prevent diabetes include maintaining a diet rich in whole grains and fiber, and choosing good fats, such as the polyunsaturated fats found in nuts, vegetable oils, and fish. Limiting sugary beverages and eating less red meat and other sources of saturated fat can also help prevent diabetes. Tobacco smoking is also associated with an increased risk of diabetes and its complications, so smoking cessation can be an important preventive measure as well (2, 4, 7).

The relationship between type 2 diabetes and the main modifiable risk factors (excess weight, unhealthy diet, physical inactivity and tobacco use) is similar in all regions of the world. There is growing evidence that the underlying determinants

of diabetes are a reflection of the major forces driving social, economic and cultural change: globalization, urbanization, population aging, and the general health policy environment (1, 3, 5).

CONCLUSION:

In outdoor patients presenting with symptoms of frequent urination, increased thirst and increased dietary habits, diabetes was found more often. Education about suitable lifestyle modifications and prevention must be ensured.

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